

THE EXPERIENCE OF DIVINE MOTIFS IN UZBEK NATIONAL NOVELS

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Abstract: The use of myths exists in all eras, when the creator wants to tell the truth about the political, social and economic life of his time, he usually uses myths. This situation can be observed in the works of Alisher Navoi, especially in the epic "Khamasa". The fact that a genius thinker and statesman like Navoi spoke about his era in the language of myths confirms the existence of a conflict between the creator and the era.

Key words: Myth, epic, divine motives, legend, perspective, nationalism, synthesis, neo-myth.

In fact, the literature of the former Soviet era, as a result of political patterns and religious restrictions, Uzbek literature was not watered with the ideas of the Holy Kur'an and Hadith, and although it did not turn to divine motives, it preserved the traditions of folk art to a certain extent. Along with the famous myths of the Turkic peoples and the Uzbek population, myths of a new content - narratives, i.e. neomyths - were created in Uzbek literature of this period.

One of the great writers of Uzbek literature, Asqad Mukhtar's novel "Plant" is a clear example of our word. The five narrations on different topics in the novel have their assigned tasks according to the idea of the work and the writer's artistic goal. The writer symbolically incorporates the words that could not be said or written during the former Soviet period into the layers of myths and legends. In addition, myths do not record specific space and time, from this point of view, it is a convenient way for a writer to use myths or create a neomyth that fits his point of view.

Askad Mukhtar also feels the need for myths in his work, and when appropriate, he points to his idea with neo-myths that reflect his artistic purpose. Jabbar Eshankul expresses this opinion about myths. It should be noted that in fiction, myths know no boundaries and do not talk about the past, on the contrary, they refer to the present and speak about today through motifs and symbolic images.

Askad Mukhtar's novel "Plant", which is told in a unique style retrospectively, is written in a new form reminiscent of eastern literary traditions. The novel talks about the ancient, recent past and present. That is,

before giving the events of the lives of Grandmother's children and grandchildren, Achil gives the narration and stories that symbolically represent this event. Those introductory stories prepare the reader for future events, serve to highlight the writer's artistic intention.

The stories that branched out in all directions like the branches of a maple tree reflected the living reality. The stories with its deep roots are about the recent past, and the narratives go back to ancient legends. The narratives, i.e. neomyths, which increased the attractiveness of the work, were able to give a deep hint of what the writer really wanted to say.

The first narration from the novel "Plant" is about a plantain planted by one of the distant ancestors of Grandmother Achil in the year of the plague. On the second Friday of the month, when the plantain should be lit, the villagers witnessed that Grandfather Achil stood under the plantain until dawn. That night, the tree does not burn and he says: "If I burn, the time will end." In the story, the maple tree acquires a symbolic meaning and is reflected as a symbol of eternity. The writer points to the immortality of Islam, the eternality of Allah in hearts in the image of the plane tree, a symbol of eternity. The author, who survived so many "floods" during the time of the conqueror Genghis, and believed that the eternal history of the Islamic religion, culture, and nation will one day be freed from the tyranny of the Shura period, and that the days of healing will come, refers to these truths in the image of grandmother Ochil, in the image of a maple tree.

Through this neo-myth-narrative created by Askad Mukhtar, he made his way even in the dangerously brutal period and expressed his opposition to the politics of the Shura era based on the mythological model. In the example of the character of grandmother Ochil, the writer is embodied before our eyes as a creator who was able to show who he is and whose side he is on, who was able to stand firm in his beliefs, and who was able to preserve the light of faith in his heart. These mythological analyzes require a new perspective on Askad Mukhtar's analysis of "Plant". The writer concentrated his main idea not on the development of events in the novel, but on the content of five narratives on different topics.

Askad Mukhtar created the first and most beautiful example of prose works based on the mythological model under the influence of Western literature, which is considered a novelty in the modern literary process, in Uzbek literature in the middle of the 20th century. Each socio-political era has a certain influence on the development of literary art, ideological poetic scope, images and stylistic

conditions. It causes its development and renewal. For example, the development of former Shura literature, including Uzbek literature, freed from the oppressive oppression of socialist realism and political patterns and reached a new era in the days of independence, began to harmonize with the most advanced principles of world literature. Such qualitative and formal changes are manifested, first of all, in the work of creative artists of middle age. Such changes can be seen, first of all, in the example of large-scale genre novels, and such large-scale works tend to glorify the national spirit, national values, restore the acquired national spiritual principles, and reflect the characteristics of its acquisition of commonality with universal ideal qualities.

Literary scholar Damin Toraev and Zebo yakhshiyeva emphasized that during the years of independence, Uzbek literature is changing and enriching in terms of content and expression, methods and styles, philosophical and spiritual analysis, and notes that a positive opposition between traditional prose and modern prose has emerged. Uzbek prose writers created modern examples of prose under the influence of writers such as Jean-Paul Sartre, Franz Kafka, Luis Borges, Albert Camus, and James Joyce, influenced by the flow of symbolism and surrealism in world literature 16.

Also, Hamidulla Karomatov, a confident and courageous scientist who decided to deeply study the harmony of Uzbek literature and Holy Koran teaches us in the early days of independence, notes with regret that Islamic ideas and themes were neglected in the creation of classic and modern literary works in our national literary studies of the 20th century. He believes that the reason for this is not that our literary experts do not understand the principles and sources of the development of literature, but in the socio-historical environment related to the Soviet.

In modern national novels, directions such as the parallel depiction of mythological plots with the unreal reality, the divine interpretation and the real reality, which were forbidden in the previous era, have become clearly visible. In particular, our skilled writer Khurshid Dostmuhammad, who made good use of the plot of ancient Greek literature, embodied the motif of loneliness in his novel "The Wise Sisyphus" in a combination of the principles of absurd and existential philosophy, national identity, and the Uzbek worldview. Its main character, the convict Sisyphus, sometimes experiences depression, sometimes social alienation, sometimes elation, sometimes hopeful moments, but most of the time he passes the divine punishment alone, alone. Considering this important aspect, effective study and mastering of the literary-aesthetic style and approaches of

the representatives of the existential and absurd direction allowed Khurshid Dostmuhammad to convincingly express the leading ideas in the novel at a high level, in accordance with the criteria of artistry.

Writers of the period of independence began to use completely new methods to reflect nationality. Nationalism is now perceived not only in external elements such as clothes, portraits, speech, but also in deep psychological analysis, symbolic and hidden of the national spirit. For example. In the story "Yak-40" by I.Sultan, Ibrahim is interested in airplanes after hearing about the Yak-40 plane from his father. But the difficulties of life do not allow him to study and work in the field of aviation, nor to go on a plane because of life's worries. He will be a baker. One day, young men studying aviation come to the bakery. They laugh at Ibrahim's simple words about the Yak-40 and talk about modern aviation and modern aircraft. But... these young men came to order bread for the wedding: "We are having a wedding," said one of them, smiling, showing his open spade teeth. "We need two thousand loaves of bread." There is a very important national scene in this episode, which does not attract the attention of the reader or even the literary critic. The size of the wedding luxuries and extravagance is reflected in the details of the wedding, which required two thousand loaves of bread. So, Uzbek is mastering the field of aviation, it is going side by side with world development, science and technology. But he was not able to get rid of his "executioner" - luxury, dreams. The writer gives a very subtle hint of one aspect of the national character.

Indeed, in the last twenty-thirty years in our literature, the artistic synthesis of divine motifs and narratives, characterized by sharp changes in the scenery of a certain period, people's daily life, and way of thinking, has risen to a new level.

References:

1. Eshonqul J. Mif va badiiy tafakkur. – Toshkent: Fan, 2019. – 312 b.
2. Hamdamov U. Badiiy tafakkur tadriji. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2002. – 199 b.
3. Jo'raqulov U. Nazariy poetika masalalari: Muallif. Janr. Xronotop. – Toshkent: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi MMIU, 2015. – 353 b.
4. Karimov B. Adabiyotshunoslik metodologiyasi. – Toshkent: Muharrir, 2011. – 88 b.
5. Matyoqubova T. Poetik idrok va mahorat. – Toshkent: "Fan va texnologiya", 2011. – 170 b
6. Мухтор А. Чинор. – Тошкент: "Ёшлар" нашриёт уйи, 2018. – 448 б.
7. Хон А. Чингиз Айтматов ва о'zbek adabiyoti. – Buxoro: Buxoro, 2005.

8. Shodmonov N. O'zbek mumtoz adabiyoti tarixi. – Toshkent: Tafakkur, 2020. – 248 b.
9. Zola, Émile. The Experimental Novel and Other Essays. Translated by Belle M. Sherman, Cassell Publishing, 1893.
10. Yakhshieva Zebo Rashidovna. Studies of the image Tamburlaine in the Russian literature field. France. Scientific approach to the modern education system. January. Part 32. P.9-12.
11. Yakhshieva Zebo Rashidovna. Scientific process of learning the personality of Tamurlaine in Russian studies. Netherland. Intellectual education, technological solutions and innovative digital tools. 2025. 3 January.
12. Yaxshiyeva Zebo Rashidovna. Ingliz va o'zbek temurshunosligi tadqiqi va taraqqiyoti. Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuvlar, nazariyaning amaliyotga tadbiqu. Toshkent. Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. 2025. Aprel.
13. Yakhshiyeva Zebo. "Aesthetic Experiments and Historical Reality in the Field of the Tetralogy." JournalNX, 2020, pp. 251-258.
14. Rashidovna Y. Z. Studies of the image tamurlaine in the field of russian oriental studies //scientific approach to the modern education system. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 32. – C. 4-6.
15. Yaxshiyeva Z. "Historical reality and its artistic interpretation" (2022): 2510-2513.

